

New life for old windows and doors

Recovery of wooden windows and doors is made possible by circular design approaches. In this way, distinctive products combining tradition with high technology keep the original charm of wooden building elements. When these windows and doors are upcycled for reuse, it can be seen as a prime example for long-life products. Wooden windows can be motorised and integrated in smart homes to enhance comfort and usability. Doors can be improved by using advanced joinery. Cases like these are of high importance as carbon in the old products remains to be stored. Furthermore, these cases help raise consumer awareness for the circular use of house elements and even to reduce the negative perceptions that exist about waste materials. Companies have even begun developing apps to improve wood recovery, which allows users to share excess wood materials.

Regional coverage and transferability

At this moment, the good practice of collection of wooden house elements such as doors and windows is presented in Eastern Europe. Regarding transferability differences of cultural building architecture must be acknowledged that can complicate disassembly. However, the practice is highly transferable to many more wood and window manufacturers within Europe and beyond. Digitalised platforms within regions can support local knowledge and awareness on disposal of wood-based materials after use and/or products.

Images: MSORA

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ Recovered wood from characteristic and/or even historical building structures (e.g., barns, mills, sheds, and residential homes) is upcycled into modern, high value products such as new wooden doors or windows.
- ▶ Supporting technologies (wood scantling or joineries)
- ▶ Modular design approach and embedded smart sensors can prevent decay and prolong product life span.
- ▶ Digitalisation concepts and tools like apps for wood sharing are innovative approaches that includes consumer perception and behaviour.